

The Influence of Perception of Value, Brand Awareness, and Customer Motivation on Purchasing Interest at Johor Summerville Residence Medan

Satyo Hadi, Endang Sulistya Rini, Beby Karina Fawzee Sembiring

Magister of Management Study Program of Postgraduate School University of Sumatera Utara

Corresponding Author: Satyo Hadi

ABSTRACT

The existence of competition between developers in developing comfortable housing and increasing prestige value, it provides many choices for potential customers. This causes Johor Summerville Residence has stagnation in house sales compared to competitor in same area. This research will examine the effect of Perception of Value, Brand Awareness, and Consumer's motivation on House Purchasing Interest. Data analysis techniques in this research used multiple linear analysis at the significance level = 0.05, conducted by 183 samples through questionnaires. The results showed that Perception of Value had a positive and significant effect on housing Purchasing Interest in Johor Summerville Medan Residence. Brand awareness has a positive and significant impact on housing Purchasing Interest in Johor Summerville Residence. Consumer's motivation has a positive and significant influence on housing Purchasing Interest in Johor Summerville Residence and the Perception of Value, brand awareness, and consumer's motivation as together have a positive and significant effect on housing Purchasing Interest at Johor Summerville Residence.

Keywords: Perception of Value, Brand Awareness, Consumer's motivation, Purchasing Interest.

INTRODUCTION

The house is the main needs of humans, in addition to food and clothing

needs, so everyone must need a place to live. Base on this, many housing developers are competing to provide house community needs on various types, such as very simple, medium and luxurious according to the needs and community purchase ability. Johor Summerville Residence is built on 5 hectares land and developed by PT. Adda Rami Jaya Land, conceptualized as luxury housing in a very strategic location. Johor Summerville Residence developed by a system that is equipped with various public facilities such as a gym, jogging track, swimming pool, and tennis court. Johor Summerville Residence is a fairly large housing complex with 312 housing units.

The interesting thing offered by Johor Summerville Residence is the unique design of each type of houses that is different from other residences in terms of quality and architecture of the building, the complete facilities provided, and the state of the environment that is comfortable and beautiful attracts consumers to buy and invest their money to buy a house in Johor Summerville Residence, so this actually gives a positive perception of its own value for prospective buyers who come. However, based on Johor Summerville Residence sales data in the period October to November 2018 did not show a significant increase compared to competitors in the same region.

Table 1 Comparison of Housing Sales Volume of Various Brands in the Medan Johor area Medan City
On October-November 2018 period

RESIDENCE	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER		
	Marketed	Sold	Percentage	Marketed	Sold	Percentage
JOHOR CITY	30 Unit	11 Unit	36,7%	19 Unit	5 Unit	26,3%
MEDAN RESORT CITY	55 Unit	17 Unit	30,1%	38 Unit	9 Unit	23,7%
JOHOR SUMMERVILLE	28 Unit	4 Unit	14,2%	24 Unit	1 Unit	4,17%

Source: Residence Data (2018)

Based on the analysis of the data above, Johor Summerville Residence needs to penetrate the market based on people's buying interest in housing. Understanding consumer behaviour is done by designing whatever consumers want, there is good brand awareness and consumer's motivation to increase purchasing ability. Consumer behaviour is the behaviour exhibited by consumers in searching for, buying, using, evaluating, and consuming products and services that they hope will satisfy their needs (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2007).

Purchasing Interest

Consumer buying interest is basically a driving factor in making purchasing decisions for a product. According to Duriyanto (2003) purchasing interest is something related to consumers' plans to buy certain products, as well as how many units of product are needed in a certain period. Interest is the behaviour that arises as a response to an object that shows the customer's desire to make a purchase (Kotler 2005). According to Suwandari (2008) the indicators of consumer buying interest are as follows:

- a. Attention, the attention of potential consumers on the products offered by producers.
- b. Interest, potential customers' interest in products offered by producers.
- c. Desire, the desire of potential consumers to have a product offered by producers.
- d. Action, prospective consumers make purchases of products offered.

Perception of Value

The perception of a high value from consumers can also affect the high desire to buy. Perception of Value according to Samuel and Wijaya (2009) is a comprehensive evaluation of the usefulness of a product based on customer perceptions

of the number of benefits to be received compared to the sacrifice made. Samuel and Wijaya (2009), argue that customer satisfaction is a comparison between the performance received and expectations, where customer satisfaction depends on the perception of customer value itself. Perceived Value is an exchange that is the principal in marketing with value as an appropriate measure of any exchange whether appropriate or not (Kotler and Keller, 2011). Customer perceived value is the difference between prospective customer valuations of all the benefits and costs of an offer against its alternatives. Perceived Value is the basis of consumers' perceptions in their evaluation comparing the benefits they receive from service providers with the sacrifice they spend to obtain these services (Kotler and Keller, 2011).

There are four indicators that can affect perceived value according to Kotler and Keller (2009):

- a. Quality Value, is the benefit obtained from the product because of the reduction of short and long term costs.
- b. Value of Money, is the benefit obtained from the perception of the expected performance of the product or service.
- c. Emotional Value, is the benefits derived from feelings or affective / positive emotions arising from consuming products.
- d. Social Value, is the benefit obtained from the product's ability to improve consumers' social self-concepts.

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness according to Duriyanto et al. (2004: 54) describe the ability of a prospective buyer to recognize, recall a brand as part of a particular product category. Meanwhile, according to Tjiptono (2014), Brand awareness (brand awareness), namely the ability of consumers to

recognize or remember that a brand is a member of certain product categories. In general, consumers tend to buy products with familiar brands on the basis of consideration of comfort, safety and others. Brand awareness is the ability of a buyer to recognize or recall that a brand is part of a particular product category. Brand awareness requires a continuum ranging from an uncertain feeling that a particular brand is known and becomes a belief that the product is the only product in its class in its category.

According to Kotler & Keller (2009), brand elements are brand-name tools that identify brands, differentiate brands, and how easily brands are remembered and recognized.

Top of mind

Top of Mind is the brand that is first mentioned by consumers or first appears in the minds of consumers. In other words, the brand is the main of various brands that exist in the minds of consumers. Top of Mind is a single response question meaning one respondent may only give one answer to this question.

Brand recall

Brand recall of the brand without assistance (unaided recall), or recall of the brand reflects the brands what respondents remember after mentioning the brand that was first mentioned.

Brand recognition

Brand Recognition is a measurement of respondent's brand awareness where

awareness is measured by providing assistance. The questions raised are assisted by mentioning the characteristics of the brand product (aided question). Questions are asked to find out how many respondents need to be reminded of the existence of the brand. Brand Recognition is a minimum level of brand awareness where brand recognition reappears after reminding through assistance.

Consumer's motivation

According to Kotler and Keller (2009) motivation is a need that is quite able to encourage someone to act. While Handoko (2001), said that motivation is a condition in a person that encourages individual desires to do certain desires in order to achieve goals. Consumer's motivation according to Sangaji and Sopiah (2013), is a drive that arises from within or from outside the self (environment) which is a driving factor towards the goals to be achieved. Associated with consumers, motivation can be interpreted as an impulse that moves consumers to decide to act towards the achievement of goals, namely to meet various kinds of needs and desires.

The indicators of consumer's motivation according to Kotler and Keller (2009) are as follows:

- a. The need for products
- b. Looking for comfort
- c. Increase prestige
- d. Feel safe

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

H1: Perception of Value Has Positive and Significant Impact on Purchasing Interest of Houses in Johor Summerville Residence.

H2: Brand Awareness Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Purchasing Interest of Houses in Johor Summerville Residence.

H3: Consumer's motivation Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Purchasing Interest of Houses in Johor Summerville Residence.

H4: Perceived Value, Brand Awareness, and Consumer's motivation simultaneously have a Positive and Significant Impact on Purchasing Interest of Houses in Johor Summerville Residence.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research used is causal descriptive research. According to Sinulingga (2017), descriptive research is a study that aims to describe systematically, factually, and accurately about the facts and properties of a particular object or population. The population of this research is prospective customers of Johor Summerville Residence who visited sample homes from November 2018 to January 2019 totalling 213 people. The sample used in this study is the total population after being reduced by 30 people used for the validity and reliability test, totalling 183 people. The research instrument used a questionnaire with measurements using a Likert Scale. Data analysis techniques in this study used multiple linear analysis at the significance level = 0.05 assisted by using SPSS v.22.0 software.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-3.973	3.030		-1.311	.192		
	Perception of Value	.354	.083	.311	4.286	.000	.854	1.171
	Brand Awareness	.251	.076	.227	3.320	.001	.963	1.038
	Consumer's Motivation	.684	.110	.457	6.201	.000	.829	1.207

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Interest

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Normality Test

Normality testing in this study aims to determine whether in the regression model, residual values are normally distributed or not. Assuming normality is the Sig. > α (0.05).

Table 2 Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		134
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	1.84556806
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.087
	Positive	.087
	Negative	-.048
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.008
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.261
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		

Source: Primary Data Processing using SPSS

Based on Table 2, the Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) value of 0.261 is known. Then it can be concluded that the residual value is normally distributed.

Linearity Test

Linearity testing in this study aims to determine whether the perceived value, brand awareness and consumer's motivation have a significant linear relationship or not to the Purchasing Interest with the assumption of Sig. the Deviation from Linearity is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. In the Linearity Test, each Sig. at Deviation from Linearity of 0.137, 0.932 and 0.297. This value is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. This shows that the perceived value, brand awareness and consumer's motivation partially have a linear relationship to purchasing interest.

Based on Table 3, Tolerance values are obtained for each of 0.854, 0.963 and 0.829. This value is greater than 0.10. Then the VIF values were 1,171, 1,038 and 1,207, respectively. This value is smaller 10. This shows that in the regression model there is no linear relationship between the independent variables (there is no multicollinearity).

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variance of the residual value. Testing heteroscedasticity in this study using the Glejser test.

Table 4 Glejser Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.370	1.913		1.238	.218
	Perception of Value	-.079	.052	-.143	-1.523	.130
	Brand Awareness	.002	.048	.004	.041	.968
	Consumer's Motivation	.091	.070	.124	1.299	.196

a. Dependent Variable: Abs_RES

Source: Primary Data Processing using SPSS

Based on Table 4, it is known the value of Sig. each of them is 0.130, 0.968, 0.196. This value is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. It can be concluded that there was no heteroscedasticity in the regression model.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 5 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-3.973	3.030		-1.311	.192
	Perception of Value	.354	.083	.311	4.286	.000
	Brand Awareness	.251	.076	.227	3.320	.001
	Consumer's Motivation	.684	.110	.457	6.201	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Interest

Source: Primary Data Processing using SPSS

Based on the results of multiple linear regression in Table 5, the regression equation is obtained as follows:

$$Y = -3,973 + 0,354X_1 + 0,251X_2 + 0,684X_3$$

The regression equation means that the perceived value, brand awareness and motivation of consumers have a positive effect on buying interest with coefficients of 0.354, 0.251 and 0.684, respectively. If the perceived value, brand awareness and consumer's motivation increase, purchasing interest will also increase. The constant value (a) of -3.973 means that if the perceived value, brand awareness and consumer's motivation have a value of 0, then the purchasing interest is of constant value of -3.973.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 6 Coefficient Determination of Perception of Value, Brand Awareness, and Consumer's Motivation Against Purchasing Interest

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.644 ^a	.415	.401	1.86674

a. Predictors: (Constant), Consumer's Motivation, Brand Awareness, Perception of Value

Based on Table 6, the R Square value of 0.415 is known. This value can be interpreted that the variable perceived value, brand awareness and consumer motivation can explain the

Purchasing Interest variable by 41.5% and the remaining 58.5% is explained by other variables not examined in this study.

Partial Hypothesis Test (t Test)

Table 7 Partial Hypothesis Test (t Test)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-3.973	3.030		-1.311	.192
	Perception of Value	.354	.083	.311	4.286	.000
	Brand Awareness	.251	.076	.227	3.320	.001
	Consumer's Motivation	.684	.110	.457	6.201	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Interest

Source: Primary Data Processing using SPSS

Based on Table 7, it is known that the perception coefficient value of 0.354 with the Sig. of 0,000. This shows that hypothesis I was accepted stating that perceived value had a positive and significant effect on housing purchase interests in Johor Summerville Residence. That is, if the perception of value increases, buying interest will increase.

The value of the brand awareness coefficient of 0.251 with the value of Sig. amounted to 0.001. This shows that hypothesis II was accepted stating that brand awareness had a positive and

significant effect on housing purchase interests in Johor Summerville Residence. That is, if brand awareness increases, buying interest will also increase.

The coefficient value of consumer motivation is 0.684 with Sig. of 0,000. This shows that hypothesis III is accepted which states that consumer motivation has a positive and significant effect on housing purchase interests in Johor Summerville Residence. That is, if consumer motivation increases, then buying interest also increases.

Test Hypotheses Simultaneously (Test F)

Table 4.25 Test Hypotheses Simultaneously (Test F)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	320.814	3	106.938	30.688	.000 ^b
	Residual	453.014	130	3.485		
	Total	773.828	133			

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Interest

b. Predictors: (Constant), Consumer's Motivation, Brand Awareness, Perception of Value

Based on Table 4.25, it is known that the F_count is 30,688 with a F_table value of 2.67 and the Sig. of 0,000. This shows that hypothesis IV was accepted stating that perceived value, brand awareness and consumer motivation had a positive and significant effect on housing purchase interests in Johor Summerville Residence.

CONCLUSION

There is a Positive and Significant Effect between Perception of Value and Purchasing Interest

Based on the research results, it is known that the perception of consumer value

towards Johor Summerville Housing is categorized as good because the quality of buildings in Johor Summerville is very good in terms of building strength, neatness of building construction, as well as the materials used. And home design in Johor Summerville is also very good and modern, with a compact layout, prioritizing natural lighting and natural air circulation. The percentage score for perceived value is 73.04%. This shows that the influence of perception is quite large in influencing consumer buying interest in homes in Johor Summerville Residence Medan.

There is a Positive and Significant Effect between Brand Awareness on Purchasing Interest

Based on research results, it is known that consumer brand awareness is categorized as good because potential consumers are able to recognize and remember the Johor Summerville brand. The percentage of brand awareness score is 71.64%. Consumers are aware of the existence of Johor Summerville Residence and are able to recognize brands, logos, or advertisements about Johor Summerville.

There is a Positive and Significant Effect between Consumer Motivation on Buying Interest

Based on the questionnaire value, it is known that consumers' motivation towards consumers' buying interest towards homes in Johor Summerville Residence Medan is categorized as good because consumers want a safe and comfortable place to live like Johor Summerville. The percentage of consumer motivation scores is 73.13%. This shows that consumer motivation in influencing consumer buying interest in homes in Johor Summerville is relatively high. The interest in buying a prospective buyer is higher if the buyer feels the housing environment is safe with a low crime rate. In addition, consumers also want to have a house that is close to public facilities such as Johor Summerville. And another motivation for someone to buy a house is because he does need a house in the near future for various reasons such as, wanting to get married in the near future, wanting to move out of the in-law's house, and an old house that cannot accommodate their needs.

There is a Positive and Significant Influence between Perception of Value, Brand Awareness and Consumer Motivation on Purchasing Interest

The results of this study indicate that the perceived value, brand awareness, and motivation of consumers simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on interest in purchasing a home in Johor Summerville Housing Medan. It is known from the results of the regression that has

been done with the results of the F_count of 30,688 with a F_table value of 2.67 and the Sig. of 0,000.

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